

Experiences of Errors and Accidents among the Healthcare Professionals of Nepal and Their Safety Expectations

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Abstract

In the workplace, errors are commonplace. Accidents rarely occur but they take toll on employee health, customer service and organizational productivity when they do. Accident researches related to errors, accidents and safety expectations are lacking. In order to shape scientific and realistic policy or introduce new safety culture and improve existing safety infrastructure, deeper understanding about healthcare professionals' experiences about these aspects is to be acquired. In the framework of grounded theory, a qualitative research was conducted using open-ended survey method by snowball sampling and analyzed thematically to fill the research gap. Total of 60 participants from various rural and urban health institutions were contacted for data. Health care employees commit two types of errors: technical and interpersonal. Their safety expectations can be described in two themes: enhanced management and better working conditions. A model has been developed based on findings from this research and named systemic safety mechanism (SSM) for health care institutions.

Keywords: Adverse events, safety culture, personal protective equipment (PPE), inadaptability, systemic safety mechanism (SSM)

Introduction

Errors and accidents (or adverse events as they cause some harms) are a common part of workplace lives. In every industry, errors occur in different forms and cause bad effects in daily operations as well as overall productivity of organizations. Errors may give stress or guilt in the employees which are bad for their well-being. They may be damaging in terms of property too. Errors may be minor or major. They sometimes might lead to accidents by increasing inadaptability which is the actual cause of accident according to a theory (Adhikari, 2017). Accidents are obviously unwanted but they occur and take toll on productivity, employee health and service delivered to customers. Some employees become second victims after accidents that are traumatizing. In medical field also, errors and accidents are rampant. From needle pricking to administration of wrong medicine, there are several errors which are sometimes detrimental and lead to accidents like death of patients. In the US alone, about one hundred thousand patients are estimated to die because of medical errors (Volpp & Grande, 2003). Employees are mindful about errors and accidents. From experiences of errors and accidents, they craft some expectations about safety measures, safety culture and safety environment. These expectations are obvious to change with times for several reasons, one being the change of technology. Safety is a major concern among many health concerns in workplace. It is very necessary to understand the employees' experiences of errors and accidents. Among healthcare professionals, exploration of their experiences of errors, accidents and safety expectations has not yet been done in

Nepal. Such research is very sparse anywhere. For framing policy to introducing safety culture in the health institutions, any framework is lacking. So, having deep insights about these experiences is very necessary for occupational health and safety of employees in medical sector.

Hazards in Medical Sector

Hazard is anything that leads to harm or damage (Runciman et al., 2007). There are several hazards for employees of healthcare industry. Nurses' and doctors' are some of the occupations that are at higher risk of occurrence of psychosocial stressors (O'Driscoll & Brough, 2010). The hazards they face are exposure to sick people who come with communicable disease, lack of resources (like suitable drugs and equipment), overload, mental pressure, emergency situation, quick decision, on-call duty, changing shifts, sharp instrument injury, unmanaged wastes, and unnecessary noise by caregiving relatives.

Errors in Medical/Healthcare Sector

Mentally ill employees in health and medicine profession commit more errors and accidents than mentally good ones. Healthcare professionals are fatigued. A study in Taiwan showed that 30.9% of such professionals were fatigued (Ho et al., 2013). Among all, younger employees were more tired. Factors related to shift work may be cause of errors or accidents. For example, a study (Gold et al., 1992) showed that nurses with changing shifts were more prone to errors and accidents than those who had same shifts. Another study in Japan (Suzuki, Kaneita et al., 2005) showed significant correlation between daytime sleepiness in nurses and occupational accidents. In an Australian study,

errors or near errors were affected by sleep deprivation (Dorrian et al., 2006). Low job control can also be a factor among the nurses and junior doctors that increases accidents. In such situation, Reason (2004) suggests medical professionals in front line to develop error wisdom which is mental preparedness to deal with contingent errors and accidents. Error reporting is seen very rare among doctors. They report errors only when protocol is violated and there are negative results (Lawton & Parker, 2002). So, there might not exist good mechanism to identify the lapses that can lead to accidents. In the workplace, human errors and system errors lead to accidents (Adhikari, 2015). Talking about human errors, fatalistic mindset can be a great cause of occupational accidents as shown by a study in Bangladesh (Patwary et al., 2012). The other causes are management weaknesses or loopholes in systems. In fact, many latent systemic factors may be the causes of accidents but researchers may be biased to attribute them to the human causes.

Accidents in Medical/Healthcare Sector

In their study, Suzuki, Ohida et al. (2004) considered four categories of medical accidents: needle-stick injury, machine operation error, patient identification error and medication error.

Relating Errors, and Accidents in Healthcare Sector

Adverse events are rarely the result of a single factor. Many causal factors cause them in combination. Some factors contributing to medication errors are poor communication, frequent interruptions (Sanghera et al., 2007), and lack of coordination. In a study, 87 cases of needle-stick accidents were recorded in five year period among which 5.4% cases caused infection of Hepatitis C Virus (Mizuno et al., 1997). The major adverse events in healthcare industry are failure of operation or procedure, infection, medication error, hospital-related injuries and wrong or missed diagnosis (Patwary et al., 2012).

Safety Expectations in Healthcare Sector

Safety is freedom from hazard (Runciman et al., 2007). No researches were found on Google Scholar about safety expectations of healthcare professionals. Zero harm is the ultimate safety expectation which may not be achievable (Ivensky, 2016). Employees want safe work environment and zero financial loss. Safety expectations are shaped by awareness and knowledge. In the globalized context, Nepalese professionals working in urban areas are also in continual communication with such practitioners abroad. Employees working in rural community setting also get educated by information about amenities, practices and policies about safety within and outside country by various means. Use of internet opens them up to a new level of awareness. It is obvious that the employees in medical field want cutting edge technology besides the essential safety infrastructure like gloves, mask, apron, staff room and rest chairs. In Nepal, accidents in workplace have seldom been studied. This study is concerned about accidents and errors in the workplace of the medical/health professionals. The modern healthcare is challenging in complex way. The errors/accident and safety issues are correspondingly complex. So, studying them should not be spared as minor issue. Moreover, qualitative researches regarding this issue are very sparse. Deeper understanding about error, accidents and occupational safety in healthcare profession demands for a qualitative inquiry. Understanding about causes and consequences of errors and accidents via experiences in workplace can give insights to prevent them in future and insights about safety expectations can be useful to establish safety culture as well as to build necessary infrastructure for occupational safety. Safety culture anticipates problems and acts actively by anonymous blameless reporting mechanism. Significant works have not been done about safety expectations. So, a new theory about safety expectations is anticipated.

Conceptual framework for the research is shown in the figure below:

Figure 1. The variables presumed to appear and relate in the research

Aim of Study

The objective of the study was to gain deep understanding about experiences of errors, to explore their effects to employees, to investigate experiences about accidents they saw from near or faced themselves, to dig deep into perceived causes of accidents, and to understand their safety expectations.

Method

The research was qualitative. Open ended survey method was used to collect data under the philosophical and methodological framework of grounded theory. Literature review was done after data were collected and partially analyzed. The participants were chosen by snowball sampling since employees in healthcare industry are very busy and organizations may not allow to use their expensive time to squander. Total of 60 participants were used for data collection. Sample size was determined by the principle of theoretical saturation. In qualitative researches, it is common practice to take principle of saturation, practical considerations (Vasileiou et al., 2018), and judgement (Sandelowski, 1995) as bases for taking sample size. They were doctors, nurses, midwives and pharmacists working all over Nepal; most of them worked in urban setting. Stoppage of data collection was guided mainly by theoretical saturation. Informed consent was taken from the participants as an ethical conduct. The privacy and confidentiality of research participants have been maintained. They were given right to withdraw. Six trained assistants were deployed for data collection. Questions were given both in Nepali and English. Some wrote answers in Nepali. Some of them wrote in English and still some of them wrote in mixed (English plus Nepali) language. The questions were open-ended. The questions are given in the appendix.

Results

Data analysis and data collection went hand in hand. Willig (2013) suggests to use in-vivo coding in grounded theory. Data analysis was conducted to discover the themes. Semi-structuredness of questionnaire already gave preset overarching themes. However, emergent themes have also been welcomed and uncovered. Major themes related to: **Experiences of Errors and Accidents**. Errors are common. There are two categories of errors medical professionals commit.

Technical Errors

Medication error is a type of error medical professionals have. Doctors prescribe mismatching medicine by mistake. Nurses sometimes mix patients' information i.e. they switch information from one patient to another. Doctors miss diagnosis. They also fail to recognize early symptoms. Sometimes, gauzes are misplaced. There is fistula breaking other times because of error of health professionals. There is intravenous site injury rarely. Wrong anesthesia may be given. They touch unsterile instruments. Pharmacists sometimes sell expired medicine. Nurses commit documentation error. Sometime they fill air in intravenous drop (in the syringe). Doctors may offer wrong treatment or prescribe antibiotics unnecessarily. There might be breach of sterility of instruments. For example, same needle may be used for many without sterilizing.

"By mistake, we sometimes sell date-expired medicine. It occurs while there are many customers... we are too occupied; we do not have time to look at everything- date and all... there should be time-to-time checking in store if medicines still have valid date" [P13, Female, 25, Pharmacist]

Interpersonal Errors

Talking rudely to patients or their people is the commonest mistake. Healthcare professionals know that they should be polite but stressing factors cause them to lose control. They lose patience, get irritated and do not interact well with patients. They do not smile at patients more often than not. They do not smile back at patients either. They also do not answer the queries of patients (properly like politely). Junior employees feel that arguing with seniors is also an error.

Medical professionals of Nepal reported that there are several types of accidents they faced or saw in their workplace. Some of them are cut injuries, ampule cut, needle prick, hydration, fall, electric shock (due to haphazardly left naked wires or damaged sockets) and chemical burns. Similarly, there are accidents while commuting to or from work. Needle prick injury is the commonest among nurses. There are physical violence by patients and visitors sometimes.

"it was my bad to talk rudely to doctors... once the relationship goes bad, it is very difficult to work with them later" [P30, Female, 31, Nurse]

Workplace Hazards

Participants reported that there are several workplace hazards they have experienced. These hazards can be divided to three major themes:

Psychological Hazards

There are seniors who like to torment newbies or juniors. They complain a lot. They adopt discipline of time rigidity and other forms of strictness. There is favoritism, nepotism and discrimination at workplace. Inequity lowers the morale. There is always fear of getting infected. This is the unconscious anxiety. Employees' own incompetence is an obstacle sometimes. In general, newbies are prone to bad behaviors of visitors and patients because of lack of both technical and interpersonal skills. Even supervisors are violent and inflict aggressive behaviors rarely. There is lack of appreciation and social support. Sleep deprivation is another hazard. Similarly, psychological factors like negligence, work pressure and hurried mentality are dangerous. Likewise, behaviors like avoidance, clumsiness and withdrawal can be destructive sometimes.

"We, new people in the field, are clumsy and seniors start showing bad emotions. There is no training from organization, just strict seniors. On top of that, patients also search for senior doctors. This is humiliating." [P59, Male, 27, Doctor]

Physical Hazards

Chemical and radiation hazards are like sword of Damocles. There is no regular lunch or dinner time. Variable food time is risky for employees' digestive health. This problem is more for nurses. Personal protective equipment (PPEs) are

inadequate. This is truer for rural areas. The nature of job itself is risky. Professionals have to work with sharp instruments. There is *fear of nosocomial* somewhere deep down in the heart. Nurses are vulnerable to violence from the patients' carers. Mostly, they abuse verbally. There are ergonomic difficulties. For example, there is very less personal space for the nurses. They have to work for long hours standing. Professional space is inadequate too. Contact with patients with communicable diseases looms large.

"You know, there are drunkards outside our office sometimes. They shout and call us by names. We fear that they will assault us with bad intention (sexually). Sometimes we are only female staff in office and it is more fearful. Not always... sometimes we have such fears" [P22, Female, 26, Auxiliary Nursing Midwife (ANM)]

Managerial Lapses

Management has failed to contain discriminatory and nepotistic practices. It has not been able to handle inequity. A person has an overload while others, especially older employees, are loafing. The hospital is congested and visitors directly access the healthcare employees, sometimes in the sensitive areas also. Some of the visitors and even patients are very aggressive. The washrooms are dirty. Healthcare professionals have to work continuously without break. Sometimes, doctors face political pressures to treat some patients with more priority and care than others.

"The toilet is so dirty... yuck! What is administration doing? There should be separate washrooms for patients and separate for us (staff)." [P32, Male, 33, Doctor]

Causes of Errors and Accidents

Fatigue is a major cause. Since medical professionals stand for a long time, they get fatigued. They also have to work in a crowded and noisy workspace, they are tired. Sometimes, the alternating shifts are a cause. Sleep deprivation is another cause of errors/accidents. There are many night duties without rest.

Patients are also to blame for errors. They do not reveal their health and disease conditions. They may hide viral status. Patients' unawareness or carelessness is costly to both patients themselves and health professionals. Health professionals are blamed for any damage. This fact is compounded by delayed lab investigations.

Degrading moral ethics or increasing unprofessional behaviors of some hospital employees are responsible for errors/accidents during health care. Since the work occurs in a team, if a team player does something avoiding codes of conduct, the outcome is damaging and everyone gets a blame. When one is mistaken, journalist defame all, reported some participants. Incompetent workmates (like those come from *reserved recruitment*) might fail the teamwork. Likewise, bad relationship in a team is detrimental to both the professionals and customers.

Wrong practices and unpreparedness are other contributing factors. Accidents can be avoided by emergency preparedness and making of practical protocol. Lack of security can be a cause of assaults to healthcare employees. Workplace congestion is also a factor to blame.

Lack of awareness or carelessness both can lead to errors. Lack of competence like not knowing how to operate machine can be a serious cause of errors/accidents. Similarly, overconfidence can lead to errors. Lack of orientation/socialization to new employees may cause lack of experience and skills, which may lead to accidents. Personal reasons like

insomnia can be harmful. Ambitions hamper because they disrupt life-work balance. Medical professionals want to grow and they have overburden of duty and study. When subordinates ignore the guidance and counseling, the outcomes may be subpar. If anything, they might lead to accidents. Distractions are not good too. Poor self-care, illness and sleep disturbance can be toxic to normal functioning.

Bad working conditions like slippery floor, very old/expired machines or littered glasses can be the cause of accident. Unmanaged workplace is a hurdle to smooth working. Congested (narrow) workspace is an impediment to normal functioning. In rural health posts, there are perils of drunkards especially to women health personnel. Lack of safety resources is troublesome. Faulty sterilization is bad.

Improper documentation, and malpractices like not abiding the precaution/protocol are likely to increase accidents. Emotional service delivery (ESD) during emergency might avoid all or some of the protocols and lead to accidents. Similarly, those who hold management positions lack *techno-management skills*. Lack of skill directly or indirectly creates an environment favorable for errors/accidents.

"I am so tired sometimes. Stand for a long time without break. Do hard work for long time. I feel like I will die. OMG! So tired. Don't they call it burnout? Errors occur mostly when I am very tired." [P56, Female, 23, Nurse]

Safety Expectations

The following themes were uncovered for safety expectations. In other words, following were the suggestions of medical professionals to prevent errors/accidents in their institutions to provide health service.

Enhanced Management

Management should be better than it is now. Most of the medical professionals are not satisfied how the hospital or health centers are managed. Participants have expressed safety expectations related to this theme in several regards. The following sub-themes have been uncovered:

Policy and Protocol

Universal safety precautions are to be adopted by the management. Institution should have a *protocol*. Based on it, there should be screenings and pre-checks of patients for communicable diseases and sent to isolation or quarantine if found positive. Healthcare employees should be vaccinated ("invest more on employees!"). There should be mechanism for cleanliness/sanitation and waste management. Policies and protocols need to

be upgraded time to time. Timely identification of risk factors is necessary. Government should punish the quacks. If quacks defame the profession, the pent up anger of public may be poured into genuine professionals.

“Wastes littered everywhere around. Broken glasses, polythene wastes. And why should not accidents occur? There should be good waste management plan here. We lose motivation to work here in messy (dirty) place. I am ashamed when my friends visit me here... They should keep this place tidy all the while. This should be according to policy” [P35, Male, 28, Doctor]

Communication

The employees should be given precautionary information timely. There should be a mechanism to communicate to visitors/carers of patients. There should be a provision for counseling the visitors.

“The patients’ visitors get angry when they do not get enough information. Management should make a mechanism to communicate to them in layman’s terms. Why should medicos get involved in things that is of no concern to them?” [P45, Male, 29, Public Health Officer].

Crowd Management and Security

The crowd should be managed. Safety policies are to be set and followed strictly. Safety policies should guide effective access of PPEs to employees. There should be enough and accessible security guards as patients and carers get aggressive towards health professionals sometimes. *“People (patients’ carers) are irrationally violent sometimes. They get so aggressive that they look like or attack like they will eat us. Guards should be standby. When called, they should come right away and handle the situation”* [P23, Female, 36, Nurse]

Respectful Organizational culture

Seniors should treat juniors with respect and obviously vice versa is true. Management should set up a culture in which supervisors cannot treat subordinates without dignity. Dignity is essential for mental health.

“They (doctors and senior nurses) treat us like we are nobody. They speak to us like we are their maidservants. Are we? At least they should show some respect. They address us ‘timi’. At least ‘tapai’ should be said.” [P07, Female, 24, Nurse]

Facilitation for Coordination

Better coordination in team is also a necessity. The managers should monitor if anybody is loafing or doing counterproductive work behaviors (CWC). Departmentalization and specialization of task are necessary as the customers in medical centers are in excess and a single person cannot do everything. There should be equity based on rewards and punishment. Employees always need motivation.

The hospitals are understaffed now. Management should add employees wherever needed. Management should arrange system for sharing problems and feedback. For example, it could keep 10 minutes’ meeting of supervisors before each weekday started. In team work, management should facilitate cooperative attitude among supervisors and seniors. All employees should be made respectively responsible.

“My friends complain that here people do not know the teamwork. There is so much carelessness. When a nurse leaves her shift, she does not complete her task and another one to take the role in another shift has to do all the things. The management should make all responsible” [P11, Male, 30, Pharmacist]

Human Resource Functions

Salary should be given timely. It also should extend emergency service. There should be facilities to quarantine the suspects with contagious diseases. Similarly, waste disposal mechanism should be in place. Management should encourage evidence based practice. For this, it should learn from mistakes or accidents and increase research to reduce them in future. Research and development department is a felt necessity. Space management should be a priority. Pre-check mechanism (like screening, blood check, etc.) should be established. For example, proper prior examination helps a lot in baby delivery in rural birthing centers. For emergency, minimal manpower should always be available at health institution. Employees should get chance for refreshment sometimes. Employees expect to be taken for hiking and picnic. They also expect physical health programs.

“We are bored doing routine tasks every day. There is minimal salary. Do they (management) know what motivation is? We want some refreshment sometimes, at least once in a year... like some picnic, cultural programs, parties... there can be many things” [P43, Female 32, Nurse]

Training

Healthcare employees want that they should be given training frequently. Their knowledge and skills should be updated. They need technical training obviously. Beside, training for interpersonal skills and conceptual skills are a necessity. New employees seek to be orientated to organizational culture. They might need clearer supervision also. Employees should also be made aware of hazards. They should be trained to be mindful and have presence of mind. Emotional intelligence should be taught. Politeness is the quality any employees should cultivate.

“As new employees, we do not know where to go, what to do. Many accidents occur due to inexperience. Training is needed to handle new equipment. We should be made aware about risk

factors” [P57, Male 25, Community Medicine Assistant (CMA)]

Better Working Conditions

There should be resting space and furniture. Long duty hours should be reduced. Night duty without rest should be changed. Artificial air all the time is sickening. So, air conditioning should be altered in a way the natural air gets in. The security mechanism should be maintained so that attempts to assault the health practitioners are aborted timely. There should be anti-radiation measures in place. Personal protective equipment (PPE) should be availed as necessary. Gloves, apron, cap, mask, X-ray shield and the like are not a luxury for health professionals. Non-functional machines should be repaired or replaced. There should be enough resources. Friendly work environment is desired. None should harass another person in any pretext. Adequate infrastructure and safety precautions are to be adopted on time. For example, side rails should be on ladders/steps. There should be good lighting. Updated computerized records of patients should be maintained and availed to health professionals whenever necessary.

“We have to work in very risky conditions without PPEs. They are not a luxury. They are essential for us. If a doctor is infected, they can infect hundreds of people.” [P58, Female, 36, Doctor]

Consequences of Hazards

There are physical and psychological consequences of workplace hazards.

There are chances of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) as in back pain, varicose vein, muscle cramp, swelling of leg, headache, etc. due to long standing and overwork. Gastritis is the result of irregular food time. The psychological consequences are burnout, exhaustion, work-family conflict, tension, tiredness and fatigue. Similarly, work stress and job dissatisfaction are other consequences. Still other psychological effects are lowered concentration, depression, anxiety and frustration. These degrade mental health of the health care employees. Degraded mental health is hurtful to service delivery at work, personal growth

and quality of life of employees. The employees should also be educated for self-care.

“I feel like not staying in this organization or even this country for a while. So risky job. Very hard work and little pay. In Australia, this much task would make much more money.” [P37, Female 26, Nurse]

Consequences of Errors/Accidents

Errors lead to punishment in different forms. Some punishments are given by management in terms of salary cut, warning and dismissal from job. Other punishments are disgusted emotions from peers or supervisors. Similarly, patients may scold or insult. Besides, they may resort to violence. Psychologically, self-confidence and self-esteem lowers. Other psychological effects are stress, guilt and remorse. The errors also lead to degradation in job satisfaction. Medical employees have to apologize sometimes. The effect is poor service. Professionals may be harmed physically like by getting infected.

Accidents lead to injuries and deaths. There might be psychological consequences like fear among patients and guilt among health practitioners. Chances are that (deadly) communicable diseases like HIV or Hepatitis may be contracted rarely to health care employees.

“In a case, I witnessed a death of baby due to error of one of our team members. I could not sleep for several days. Still, I feel like crying when I remember that. That was the incident of time when I had just joined this hospital” [P20, Male 34, Doctor]

Accept Errors

An emergent theme is that errors are always a lesson. They should be accepted. Even though healthcare system (including managerial lapses and inadequacy) is majorly responsible for the errors (and accidents), some errors are inevitable. Employees should try not to repeat them by learning from them. Organization can use errors and accidents as opportunities to learn and increase safety in future. Errors are a great resource for safety climate if utilized wisely.

“Every error is a lesson. Despite all the efforts, errors occur once in a while. Accidents occur rarely sometimes” [P16, Female, 28, Health assistant]

Figure 2. Major themes about errors and safety expectations

Discussion

In qualitative way, the issues related to errors, hazards and accidents have seldom been studied. Study of this nature is almost non-existent in healthcare sector in Nepal. The qualitative data in this study were collected by open-ended survey method until theoretical saturation was achieved. Themes related to phenomena were uncovered. The findings are hopefully helpful to private and public hospitals and also health centers to improve infrastructure and culture related to safety of both health professionals and patients. The government can be benefited in order to frame new or revise existing policies regarding occupational safety in medical industry. This research aimed to have insights about nature of errors/accidents and safety expectations for making up of a new theory. The kind of accidents experienced by healthcare professionals are similar to those experienced by others outside Nepal as reported in Vaz et al. (2010) like needle prick injuries. Needlestick injuries occur during recapping of needles and while breaking injection ampoules in Nigeria (Nwoga et al., 2020). Some participants in this study also reported that they get such injuries while breaking ampoules. As the participants here reported the fear of hepatitis infection, a study in Brazil established that work-related injuries among health workers increased chances of such infection by more than four times (Ciorlia & Zanetta, 2005).

regards can lead to errors and accidents.

Conclusion

The following model (refer to figure 3) has been developed based on how research participants responded to various questions asked to them about hazards, errors, accidents and their safety expectations. This model has been named systemic safety mechanism (SSM) and is applicable to healthcare institutions like hospitals and health centers.

The errors/accidents are a resource to learn. They are inevitable. So, they should be used as feedback to enhance safety climate at hospitals or other health centers. Proactively, the health institutions should have research unit to deal errors/accidents issues. There should be good and updated policies for safety of health professionals and patients. Crowd management, security guards, initial screening of patients for communicable diseases, etc. are some of the expectations of medical professionals. Other factors like communication mechanism with patients is also helpful for safety. While serving, healthcare professionals should get to use PPEs and have access to security guards whenever they want. Moreover, there should be good working conditions in a healthy workspace. Physical infrastructure also should be adequate. Inadequacy in all these

Figure 3. Systemic Safety Mechanism (SSM) for healthcare institutions like hospital

Limitations of Research

The research was generalized attempt to discover the errors/accidents of medical professionals and was not focused to particular profession (like doctors, nurses, lab technicians) or occupations (like pharmacists, health assistants, auxiliary nursing midwives). It has used the self-report method. Subjective experiences are not always accurate. All the experience might not have been recollected. The better method would have been diary method in which professionals are made maintain diary over a long period of time. Another better methodological alternative would be ethnography. This research has used snowball sampling which cannot be considered a strong selection method. Similarly, the safety expectations are different for urban and rural contexts. So, separate research with rural focus and research with urban focus would have solicited better and finer results. The experiences of errors can be better captured in narrative analysis. The research participants were mostly entry level or mid-level medical professionals. Issues related to top-tier professionals who are generally older than the research participants in this study might not have been explored from this research.

Future Researches

Future researches can investigate each specific profession particularly. The future researches can also verify the model come from this research. There should be investigations about nature of errors/accidents and safety expectations for rural setting and urban setting separately. Similarly, it appears narrative research would better explore experiences of accidents.

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Appendix

The Questions Asked to The Participants

- What kind of errors do you usually commit while working?
- Please share some examples of minor errors you committed in the workplace.
- What errors do you often recall or never forget?
- How did those errors recur at work?
- What were the consequences of those errors?
- In the duration of ## years of your working in this organization, what kind of accidents did you face?
- What caused them?
- In the duration of ## years of your working in this organization, what kinds of accidents did you see?
- What do you think were the causes of those accidents?

- What are the hazards in your workplace that endanger your physical health?
- What are the hazards in your workplace that endanger your mental health?
- What safety measures are satisfactory in your workplace?

- What safety measures are lacking in your workplace?
- What best safety measures do you know of in your field?
- How have safety measures changed and how do you hope them to change?